

Effects of Leadership Styles of School Heads to Mental Health Status and Job Performance of Elementary School Teachers in the Division of Lucena City

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Article Details:

Received: 25 February 2026

Revised: 27 February 2026

Accepted: 04 March 2026

Published: 07 March 2026

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Recommended Citation:

Canas, R. A., Jalos, L. M. (2026). Effects of Leadership Styles of School Heads to Mental Health Status and Job Performance of Elementary School Teachers in the Division of Lucena City. *The International Review of Multidisciplinary Research*, 1 (3), 93-106. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18897824>

Index Terms:

leadership styles, mental health, job performance, work-life balance, teachers, education

Abstract. This study examined the effect of leadership styles school heads on the mental health status and job performance of elementary school teachers in the Division of Lucena City, using a descriptive–correlational research design. A stratified random sampling technique was employed to select respondents from selected public elementary schools, which included school heads and teachers. Data were gathered using validated survey questionnaires and were analyzed using descriptive statistics such as mean and standard deviation, as well as regression analysis. The findings revealed that Transactional Leadership was the most commonly practiced leadership style among school heads. Results also showed that teachers demonstrated a high level of mental health status, indicating emotional resilience, effective coping strategies, and the ability to maintain work–life balance. Furthermore, teachers’ job performance was rated Outstanding, particularly in the areas of professionalism, collaboration, learner support, and commitment to teaching responsibilities. Statistical analysis indicated that there was no significant relationship between school heads’ leadership styles and teachers’ mental health status ($p = 0.412$) as well as teachers’ job performance ($p = 0.498$). However, the study revealed a significant positive correlation ($r = 0.336$) between teachers’ mental health status and job performance. This suggests that teachers who experience better mental well-being tend to demonstrate higher levels of effectiveness, engagement, and productivity in their professional duties. The results highlight the importance of supporting teachers’ mental health as a key factor in improving job performance. Based on the findings, an intervention program focusing on leadership empowerment, mental wellness, and stress management was proposed to sustain teacher well-being and promote a supportive and high-performing school environment.

Introduction

Leadership plays a pivotal role in shaping the effectiveness and well-being of individuals within any educational setting. In the context of elementary schools, the leadership style of school heads significantly influences not only the academic performance of students but also the mental health and overall performance of teachers. Teachers, being at the heart of the learning process, face numerous challenges in their roles, from managing classroom dynamics to meeting diverse student needs. It is widely recognized that supportive leadership can be a crucial factor in mitigating stress and promoting professional growth.

To demonstrate instructional leadership, school heads are expected to ensure that teachers have the necessary support for their professional growth. This includes managing the implementation of the curriculum and coordinating it with the school’s objectives for student success. To improve instructional quality, school heads should actively participate in regular classroom observations and provide constructive feedback to enhance the quality of instruction. The National Adoption and Implementation of the Philippine Professional Standards for School Heads (PPSSH), as outlined in DepEd Order No. 24,

s. 2020 sets clear expectations for the roles of school heads, particularly in how they interact with and support teachers. The PPSSH provides a competency framework for school heads to follow, and one of their key responsibilities is to create an environment that fosters teacher development and improves overall teaching and learning within the school. The Philippine Professional Standards for School Heads (PPSSH) emphasizes that school heads play a critical role in supporting, guiding, and developing teachers. Their leadership is vital to creating a thriving educational environment that ultimately leads to better outcomes for students and a more positive and effective school culture. Additionally, in the Philippine Educational system, school principals have the greatest contribution in terms of maintaining school performance. As stated in Republic Act 9155, also known as the Governance of Basic Education Act of 2001, the law primarily focuses on restructuring the governance and management of the Philippine basic education system. But every leader has a certain talent. Nobody must possess all the necessary traits for leadership. Successful school heads are those who establish the role of being a leader who builds strong leadership to achieve a progressive goal of the school's vision and mission (Estacio, 2022).

The success of the school lies not only in the supervision of the good school leader but also in the help of public-school teachers. As stated in Republic Act No. 4670, a teacher is defined as "A teacher is any person engaged in the practice of teaching in the elementary, secondary, or tertiary levels in schools under the supervision of the Department of Education, the Commission on Higher Education (CHED), or the Technical Education and Skills Development Authority (TESDA), including those who are teaching in non-formal education and in institutions for special education." Teachers play a vital role in the Philippines' Education, and it is relevant to study the influence of the school leaders on the mental health and performance of the elementary teachers. The importance of teacher mental health in the teaching profession is emphasized, as teachers play a multifaceted role beyond imparting knowledge, impacting student outcomes, and improving the overall quality of education. Teacher well-being is closely linked to student learning, and recognizing the mental health challenges teachers face is vital to preventing negative consequences for both educators and students. The teaching profession is a vital pillar of any education system, shaping the intellectual and emotional development of future generations. As educators, teachers shoulder the responsibility of imparting knowledge, fostering critical thinking, and nurturing the overall well-being of their students. However, the demands and challenges of the teaching profession can have a profound impact on the mental health of educators. (Yue, 2024).

The research findings of Yue (2024) revealed a diverse range of leadership styles at BUBA, impacting teacher mental health. Collaborative and supportive leadership styles are associated with positive teacher mental health, fostering a conducive work environment. Authoritarian and directive styles, on the other hand, contribute to stress and dissatisfaction among teachers. Factors within leadership styles, such as professional development and recognition, further influence teacher well-being. Additionally, in the study by Cardinez and Mahinay (2023), it was found that 75.5% of the respondents had a normal level of stress, and 0.5% reported being extremely severely stressed. Forty-four percent (44%) manifested a moderate level of anxiety, and 7% experienced mild anxiety. Most of the respondents have a normal level of depression (44.8%), but it can be noted that teachers who declared experiencing a moderate level of depression follow at 33% and only 1% of the respondents claimed to be extremely severely depressed. The study also found that teachers have good emotional and physical health conditions. The mental health state of teachers in terms of stress, anxiety, and depression was alarming. Moderate anxiety and depression can worsen if not addressed.

To promote and protect the mental health and well-being of learners, teachers, and school personnel in the basic education sector, President Ferdinand R. Marcos Jr. signed Republic Act No. 12080, also known as the "Basic Education Mental Health and Well-Being Promotion Act," on December 9, 2024, during a ceremonial signing held at Malacañang Palace. The Implementing Rules and Regulations (IRR) of Republic Act No. 12080 provide the necessary guidelines for the effective enforcement of the Act and shall hereinafter be referred to as "the Act." These IRRs outline the mechanisms, responsibilities, and structures required for proper implementation. Their primary purpose is to ensure the integration of mental health into the education system through preventive, promotive, and responsive interventions. The IRR also aims to develop policies, programs, and services that address the mental health needs of the basic education community, thereby creating a safe, supportive, and inclusive learning environment for all.

In the Division of Lucena City, promotion of mental health awareness is through various programs and initiatives, particularly in the educational sector. Institutions like Lucena City National High School (LCNHS) have organized seminars and workshops to raise awareness about stress management, emotional well-being, and coping strategies. The Department of Education collaborates with mental health professionals to integrate mental health education into the curriculum. The City Health Office provides accessible mental health services through partnerships with local healthcare providers and organizations.

But despite these initiatives, there has been a growing concern over the mental health and job performance of elementary school teachers in the Division of Lucena City in recent years. Teachers in this context face increasing pressures, including

heavy workloads, shifting policies, and rising student populations. This results in resigning, working abroad, a change of career, and the like. While these challenges are well-documented, a crucial yet often overlooked factor is the role of school heads' leadership styles in shaping teachers' work experiences and well-being. Leadership practices that fail to support teachers, such as poor communication, lack of emotional support, micromanagement, and inconsistent decision-making, can contribute to heightened stress, burnout, and feelings of isolation. These issues, in turn, directly impact teachers' ability to perform effectively in the classroom. Despite the critical role leadership plays in influencing school climate, teacher mental health, and job satisfaction, there is a lack of local research that examines these connections in the specific context of Lucena City's diverse and highly urbanized school system. Without a clear understanding of how leadership styles affect teachers' mental health and performance, efforts to improve school outcomes and teacher retention remain limited.

Research Questions

This study aims to assess the effects of leadership styles school heads to mental health status and job performance of elementary school teachers in the Division of Lucena City. Specifically, this study will seek to answer the following questions:

1. What prevailing leadership styles are practiced by school heads in the elementary schools in the Division of Lucena City?
2. What is the mental health status of elementary school teachers in the Division of Lucena City in terms of:
 - 2.1 stress level,
 - 2.1 emotional well-being and
 - 2.2 work-life balance?
3. What is the level of job performance of elementary school teachers in the Division of Lucena City in terms of:
 - 3.1 instructional competence,
 - 3.2 classroom management,
 - 3.3 professionalism and ethical conduct,
 - 3.4 collaboration and communication,
 - 3.5 commitment and continuous learning and
 - 3.6 learner outcome support?
4. What is the effect of leadership style of school heads to the following:
 - 4.1 mental health status
 - 4.2. level of job performance of elementary school teachers?
5. What intervention program can the researcher suggest to improve leadership practice of school heads and to support mental health and job performance of elementary school teachers?

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed a descriptive-correlational research design to describe the leadership styles of school heads and determine their relationship to the mental health status and job performance of elementary school teachers in the Division of Lucena City. As explained by Creswell (2023), a descriptive-correlational design aims to describe existing conditions and examine the degree of relationship between two or more variables without manipulating them. In this study, data were collected through validated survey questionnaires to obtain a factual representation of how leadership styles are practiced and how they relate to teachers' well-being and professional performance. Statistical tools such as mean, standard deviation, and Pearson correlation were utilized to analyze the data and determine relationships among variables. While this design allows the researcher to identify trends and associations between leadership style, mental health, and job performance, it does not establish a cause-and-effect relationship. Instead, it provides an evidence-based understanding of how these variables interact in the natural school setting, serving as a foundation for future interventions and leadership development programs.

By employing this design, the study provided an overview of how school leadership styles were associated with teacher well-being and effectiveness in their roles, without attempting to manipulate the leadership behavior or intervene in the school environment. This approach is practical and ethical for educational settings where experimental manipulation is often not feasible.

Respondent /Participants

The respondents of this study consisted of elementary school heads and teachers from selected public elementary schools in the Division of Lucena City. The total population of the division includes forty-four (44) school heads and one thousand two hundred forty-two (1,242) elementary school teachers. From this population, a sample of twelve (12) public elementary schools was selected, representing the four districts North, East, West, and South, and encompassing schools classified as small, medium, and large.

From the selected schools, twelve (12) school heads and three hundred eighty-five (385) elementary school teachers served as respondents. Specifically, the North District included three (3) schools with 80 teachers, the East District had three (3) schools with 92 teachers, the West District comprised three (3) schools with 145 teachers, and the South District included three (3) schools with 68 teachers.

The inclusion of schools from different districts and varying sizes ensured a more comprehensive representation of the population in the Division of Lucena City. This stratification allowed the study to capture potential differences in leadership styles across contexts, as well as variations in the mental health status and job performance of teachers based on school size and setting. The sample size was deemed sufficient to provide reliable data for analysis while maintaining manageability for the researcher. By including both school heads and teachers, the study was able to gather perspectives from leaders and subordinates, which is crucial in examining the effects of school heads' leadership styles on teachers' mental health and job performance.

Instrument of the Study

The research instrument for this study utilized three questionnaires. The first instrument used the self-made questionnaire to assess the leaders' styles of the school heads such as transactional, transformational, laissez-faire, autocratic, democratic, charismatic and servant styles. The instrument was presented to the expert and subject for comments and suggestions. After editing it will be submitted for final validation.

The second research instrument used the self-made questionnaire to determine the mental health status of the elementary school teachers. The instrument was presented to the expert and subject for comments and suggestions. After editing it was submitted for final validation. And lastly to determine the job performance level of the elementary school teachers, the researcher also crafted a survey questionnaire. The instrument was presented to the expert and subject for comments and suggestions. After editing it will be submitted for final validation.

Procedure

To gather the data, the following procedures was done. The researcher sought approval from the Division of Lucena City Education Office and the respective schools. Consent forms was distributed to the teachers and school heads, ensuring confidentiality and voluntary participation. The questionnaires were distributed to teachers across selected schools. Teachers was given sufficient time to complete the surveys, with assistance available if needed. The survey was administered in both paper and online formats to ensure accessibility. And lastly, data collected from the questionnaires and interviews was compiled, and prepared for analysis.

Data Analysis

The data gathered in the study were analyzed and interpreted using appropriate descriptive and inferential statistical tools. Descriptive statistics such as frequency distribution, mean, and percentage were used to describe the respondents' perceptions and responses regarding leadership styles of school heads, teachers' mental health status, and teachers' job performance.

A five-point Likert scale was utilized to interpret the responses for each variable. Leadership styles were measured in terms of the extent to which leadership behaviors were practiced, mental health status was assessed based on the degree of agreement with mental health-related statements, and job performance was evaluated according to the frequency with which performance indicators were observed. Each scale was supported by corresponding verbal interpretations and qualitative descriptions to ensure clarity and consistency in data interpretation.

To determine the influence of school heads' leadership styles on teachers' mental health status and job performance, Regression Analysis was employed. Furthermore, Correlation Analysis was used to examine the relationship between teachers' mental health status and their level of job performance.

These statistical treatments provided a systematic and comprehensive basis for analyzing the data and drawing valid conclusions relevant to the objectives of the study.

Ethical Considerations

Prior to the conduct of the study, the researcher sought formal permission from the school head to allow the administration of the research within their respective institutions. Likewise, the voluntary participation of teachers as respondents was obtained with their informed consent. No respondent was compelled to take part, and they were given the freedom to decline or withdraw from the study at any point without any consequences.

The researcher fully respected the rights, safety, and confidentiality of all participants. The objectives and purpose of the study were clearly explained to ensure informed participation. All information and responses provided were handled with the utmost confidentiality and were secured using appropriate protective measures to prevent unauthorized access. Moreover, potential risks associated with participation were carefully considered. The study was designed to avoid causing physical, psychological, social, or professional harm to the respondents. The overall welfare and dignity of the participants remained the highest priority throughout the research process.

The researcher also declared that she has no financial, personal, or professional conflict of interest that may influence the conduct, analysis, or reporting of this study entitled "Effects of Leadership Styles School Heads to Mental Health Status and Job Performance of Elementary School Teachers in the Division of Lucena City."

This research was conducted solely for academic purposes as part of the requirements for graduate study. The researcher affirmed that the study was carried out objectively and ethically, without any intention to favor or prejudice any individual, group, or institution involved. Should any potential conflict of interest arise during the course of the study, the researcher commits to immediately disclose it to the appropriate authority.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the findings according to the study's research questions.

Part I. Leadership Style practiced by the School Heads in the Elementary Schools in the Division

School	Leadership Style	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Ilayang Dupay Elementary School	<i>Transactional Leadership</i>	3.51	Frequently Practiced
San Lorenzo Elementary School	<i>Democratic Leadership</i>	3.05	Occasionally Practiced
Elvira Razon Aranilla Elementary School	<i>Transactional Leadership</i>	3.03	Occasionally Practiced
Lucena East IX Elementary School	<i>Democratic Leadership</i>	3.41	Frequently Practiced
Lucena East III Elementary School	<i>Democratic Leadership</i>	2.99	Occasionally Practiced
Lucena East I Elementary School	<i>Transactional Leadership</i>	3.34	Occasionally Practiced
Ilayang Talim Elementary School	<i>Democratic Leadership</i>	3.41	Frequently Practiced
Salinas Elementary School	<i>Transactional Leadership</i>	3.02	Occasionally Practiced
Lucena West I Elementary School	<i>Transactional Leadership</i>	3.25	Occasionally Practiced
BLISS Elementary School	<i>Transactional Leadership</i>	3.41	Frequently Practiced
Mayao Parada Elementary School	<i>Democratic Leadership</i>	3.03	Occasionally Practiced
Mayao Crossing Elementary School	<i>Transactional Leadership</i>	3.26	Occasionally Practiced

Table 1. Prevailing Leadership Styles of School Heads

Table 1 presents the prevailing leadership styles practiced by school heads in the elementary schools within the Division of Lucena City. The results reveal that the Transactional Leadership Style (TSL) and Democratic Leadership Style (DL) are the most commonly practiced among school heads. Specifically, seven schools were led by principals exhibiting Transactional Leadership, while five schools practiced the Democratic Leadership approach.

The mean scores for both styles range from 2.99 to 3.51, interpreted as "Occasionally Practiced" to "Frequently Practiced." Notably, Ilayang Dupay Elementary School (M = 3.51) and BLISS Elementary School (M = 3.41) demonstrated the highest mean scores, suggesting that their school heads frequently apply transactional principles in managing their schools.

These findings imply that most school heads in the division emphasize accountability, supervision, and structured management, which are characteristics of the transactional style, while also promoting participative decision-making and

collaboration typical of democratic leadership. This combination indicates a balanced approach where school heads maintain control and order while encouraging teacher involvement in school operations.

Overall, the results suggest that Transactional Leadership is the prevailing leadership style among elementary school heads in the Division of Lucena City. This reflects a management approach focused on task completion, performance monitoring, and reward-based motivation complemented by elements of democratic leadership that foster teamwork and teacher engagement, aligning with the goal of maintaining effective and harmonious school environments.

The findings of the study revealed that Transactional Leadership emerged as the dominant leadership style among school heads in the Division of Lucena City, as reflected in seven out of twelve schools. This result aligns with the study of Cabillar (2024), who found that transactional leadership was one of the most influential styles affecting teacher commitment in public schools in Panabo City. The study emphasized that transactional leaders are often effective in maintaining order, ensuring performance accountability, and promoting compliance with institutional policies, qualities that are highly valued in the bureaucratic structure of the Philippine public school system. Similarly, Torres (2023) found that among transformational, transactional, and laissez-faire leadership styles, only transactional leadership had a significant effect on beginning teachers' performance in the Schools Division of San Jose del Monte, Bulacan. This supports the notion that transactional leadership, which focuses on rewards, supervision, and goal attainment, is often adopted by school heads to meet performance targets and uphold institutional efficiency.

The dominance of transactional leadership among school heads may be attributed to the highly structured and results-oriented nature of the Philippine public-school system. School heads are expected to comply with strict DepEd policies, performance indicators, and accountability measures such as RPMS, SBM standards, and school performance targets. These institutional demands encourage leadership practices that emphasize supervision, compliance, performance monitoring, and reward-based motivation. Additionally, large teacher populations, limited resources, and heavy administrative workloads may lead school heads to rely on transactional approaches as an efficient means of maintaining order, ensuring task completion, and meeting organizational expectations within constrained school environments.

However, the presence of Democratic Leadership in several schools suggests that collaboration and participatory management are also recognized leadership practices in the division. This is consistent with the findings of Intud and Fernal (2025), who reported that while transactional leadership remains prevalent among school heads, democratic and servant leadership elements are increasingly evident as school administrators aim to improve teacher engagement and morale. Overall, these findings indicate that while the transactional approach remains the predominant framework guiding school leadership in Lucena City, there is a gradual integration of democratic and servant-oriented practices that foster a more supportive and participatory school environment.

Overall, the findings reveal that while school heads in Lucena City primarily adhered to transactional leadership principles, elements of democratic leadership were also evident. These results imply a balance between traditional management practices and emerging leadership approaches aimed at fostering teacher engagement and organizational commitment.

Part II. Mental Health Status of Elementary School Teachers in the Division of Lucena City

Mental Health Status		Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1	Stress Level	3.34	<i>Moderate Stress Level</i>
2	Emotional Well-Being	3.83	<i>High Emotional Well-Being (HEWB)</i>
3	Work-Life Balance	3.55	<i>High Work-Life Balance (HWLB)</i>
Combined Mean		3.57	<i>High Mental Health Status (HMHS)</i>

Table 2. Mental Health Status of Elementary School Teachers in the Division of Lucena City

Table 2 presents the Mental Health Status of Elementary School Teachers in the Division of Lucena City, which summarizes three components—stress level, emotional well-being, and work-life balance. The combined mean of 3.57, interpreted as High Mental Health Status (HMHS), indicates that teachers in the division generally maintain positive mental health despite the challenges of their profession. Among the three indicators, emotional well-being obtained the highest mean score of 3.83, interpreted as High Emotional Well-Being (HEWB). This suggests that teachers experience positive emotions, resilience, and satisfaction in their professional roles. Work-life balance followed with a mean of 3.55 (High Work-Life Balance), reflecting that teachers are able to manage their professional and personal responsibilities effectively. Meanwhile, stress level recorded the lowest mean at 3.34, interpreted as Moderate Stress Level, implying that while teachers do

encounter pressure from their workload and responsibilities, it remains at a manageable level. The data reveal that even though stress is a common experience among teachers, it does not significantly compromise their emotional well-being and ability to balance work and personal life.

These findings imply that teachers in Lucena City demonstrate emotional strength, adaptability, and coping mechanisms that allow them to maintain mental wellness amid their demanding tasks. Their high emotional well-being suggests the presence of positive factors such as supportive school environments, collegial relationships, and effective leadership that foster a sense of belonging and job satisfaction. Likewise, their high work–life balance indicates that teachers can allocate time for both their professional duties and personal lives, helping to buffer the effects of occupational stress. However, the moderate stress level also signals that teachers continue to face challenges related to workload, administrative demands, and expectations. This balance between moderate stress and high well-being highlights the resilience of teachers, who continue to perform effectively while maintaining mental and emotional stability.

The results are consistent with recent Philippine studies that explore the mental health and well-being of public-school teachers. For instance, a study by Work-Related Burnout on Psychological Well-Being among Public School Teachers: Resilience as Moderating Factor (2023) found that public school teachers maintained high psychological well-being despite experiencing burnout. The study emphasized the importance of resilience as a protective factor that enables teachers to cope with work-related stress and sustain positive emotional states. Similarly, Batiacila and Monteroso (2025) revealed that work–life balance mediates the relationship between teacher stress and performance among public school teachers in Samal City. Their findings showed that while teachers experience stress, maintaining a high work–life balance enhances performance and prevents stress from escalating into burnout. Furthermore, The Impact of Work Stress on the Psychological Well-Being of Public Elementary School Teachers (2024) reported that even under stressful conditions, teachers' psychological well-being remained high, mainly due to supportive relationships, optimism, and intrinsic motivation. These studies support the current data, confirming that teachers who cultivate resilience, balance, and emotional regulation tend to experience high overall mental health despite occupational pressures.

In conclusion, the findings underscore that teachers in the Division of Lucena City possess commendable levels of emotional well-being and work–life balance, which help maintain their high overall mental health status. The moderate stress level observed serves as a reminder that while teachers can manage their pressures, continuous institutional support is essential. School administrators and policymakers should strengthen programs that promote mental wellness, such as stress management workshops, wellness breaks, and peer support groups. Leadership styles that emphasize empathy, communication, and shared decision-making can also play a vital role in sustaining teachers' well-being. Ultimately, fostering a supportive and balanced school environment not only enhances teachers' mental health but also contributes to improved job performance and educational outcomes.

Part III. Level of Job Performance of Elementary School Teachers in the Division of Lucena City

Domains	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
I. Instructional Competence	4.48	Very Satisfactory
II. Classroom Management	4.56	Outstanding
III. Professionalism and Ethical Conduct	4.59	Outstanding
IV. Collaboration and Communication	4.60	Outstanding
V. Commitment to Continuous Learning	4.49	Very Satisfactory
VI. Learner Outcomes and Support	4.60	Outstanding
Overall Mean	4.55	Outstanding

Table 3. Level of Job Performance of Elementary School Teachers in the Division of Lucena City

The table presents the Level of Job Performance of Elementary School Teachers in the Division of Lucena City, covering six key domains: instructional competence, classroom management, professionalism and ethical conduct, collaboration and communication, commitment to continuous learning, and learner outcomes and support. The data reveal that teachers in the division demonstrate a high level of performance, with an overall mean of 4.55, verbally interpreted as Outstanding. Among the domains, the highest ratings were observed in Collaboration and Communication and Learner Outcomes and Support (mean = 4.60), followed closely by Professionalism and Ethical Conduct (mean = 4.59) and Classroom Management (mean = 4.56), all interpreted as Outstanding. Meanwhile, Instructional Competence (mean = 4.48) and Commitment to Continuous Learning (mean = 4.49) were rated Very Satisfactory. These findings indicate that Lucena City's elementary

school teachers exhibit strong professionalism, effective classroom management, and a high degree of collaboration, contributing positively to learner success.

The results further suggest that teachers in Lucena City consistently uphold ethical standards, maintain positive communication with peers and stakeholders, and implement practices that lead to favorable learner outcomes. The Very Satisfactory scores in instructional competence and continuous learning imply areas for potential improvement—particularly in adopting more innovative teaching strategies and engaging in sustained professional development. These findings align with national and regional studies highlighting that Filipino teachers generally perform at high levels in key teaching domains but require ongoing training to maintain effectiveness in evolving educational contexts.

Recent research supports these outcomes. Sajonia and Gabion (2025) found that teachers in Guimaras State University displayed very high levels of instructional competence and classroom management skills, mirroring Lucena teachers' strong ratings. Similarly, Loyola (2025) reported a positive relationship between teachers' instructional competence and pupils' academic performance in Eastern Samar, underscoring the direct link between teaching performance and learner achievement. Lazaro (2025) also confirmed that teacher performance ratings are significantly correlated with student outcomes in multi-grade classrooms, further validating the strong learner outcomes observed in Lucena City. In Davao City, Pana and Baguio (2024) highlighted that teachers with high professionalism and leadership behaviors foster improved collaboration and communication—two of the highest-scoring domains in the present data. Moreover, Antiola and Fernal (2025) demonstrated that continuous participation in the School Learning Action Cell (SLAC) program enhanced teachers' instructional competence, emphasizing the importance of professional learning in maintaining high performance. Complementing these, Salavacion, Satojito, and Martir (2025) found that innovative strategies significantly influenced learner engagement and performance, reinforcing the high ratings of Lucena teachers in learner outcomes and support.

Overall, the findings from Lucena City align with recent empirical studies, showing that Filipino teachers continue to exhibit outstanding job performance characterized by professionalism, collaboration, and dedication to learner development. While teachers are already achieving commendable results, sustained investment in continuous learning and instructional innovation will be key to maintaining and enhancing this level of excellence

Part IV. Effect of Leadership Style School Heads

Indicators	r - Correlation	p - Value	Interpretation
Mental	0.042	0.412	Not Significant
Job Performance	0.035	0.498	Not Significant
Mental - Job Performance	0.336	0.00001	Significant

Table 4. Effect of Leadership Style of School heads to the Mental Health Status and Job Performance of Teachers

The table presents the effect of school heads' leadership style on the mental health status and job performance of elementary school teachers in the Division of Lucena City. The correlation between school heads' leadership style and teachers' mental health status yielded a very weak positive correlation ($r = 0.042$) with a p-value of 0.412, which is higher than the 0.05 level of significance. This result indicates that school heads' leadership style has no significant effect on the mental health status of elementary school teachers. Variations in leadership approaches do not significantly influence teachers' psychological well-being.

Similarly, the relationship between school heads' leadership style and teachers' job performance revealed a very weak positive correlation ($r = 0.035$) with a p-value of 0.498, also exceeding the level of significance. This finding shows that school heads' leadership style does not have a significant effect on the level of teachers' job performance. Teachers' performance levels appear to remain stable regardless of the leadership style employed by school heads.

These results suggest that teachers' mental health and job performance are likely influenced more by personal, professional, and organizational factors such as intrinsic motivation, emotional resilience, workload management, peer support, and established performance standards rather than leadership style alone. The absence of a significant effect implies that elementary school teachers in the division may possess strong professional autonomy and coping mechanisms that enable them to maintain well-being and performance independently of leadership variations.

However, it also reveals a statistically significant moderate positive relationship between teachers' mental health and job performance ($r = 0.336$, $p = 0.00001$). This indicates that while leadership style does not directly affect mental health or

performance, teachers with better mental health tend to perform more effectively in their jobs. This finding highlights mental health as a critical factor in sustaining high levels of teacher performance.

Recent research supports these findings. Mphaluwa et al., (2025) found that leadership styles do not always directly influence employee performance unless mediated by employee engagement and motivation, highlighting the crucial role of intrinsic factors in translating leadership effectiveness into improved performance outcomes. Similarly, Afsar et al. (2021) revealed that the impact of leadership on mental health is often indirect, influenced by organizational climate and employees' psychological resilience. Moreover, Nguyen et al. (2023) emphasized that the relationship between leadership and job performance tends to weaken when employees experience autonomy and self-regulation, suggesting that leadership effects vary depending on workplace context and employee independence.

Overall, the findings clearly answer SOP 4 by indicating that school heads' leadership style has no significant effect on teachers' mental health status and job performance, while emphasizing that mental health itself plays a significant role in influencing teachers' performance. These results underscore the importance of prioritizing mental health interventions and wellness programs alongside leadership practices to enhance teacher effectiveness.

The result of the study implies that variations in leadership approaches, whether transactional, democratic, or other styles, do not directly influence teachers' psychological well-being or their work efficiency. Therefore, the null hypothesis stating that there is no significant effect on the school head's leadership style on the teachers' job performance and mental health status is accepted. On the other hand, results revealed that teachers' mental well-being has a statistically significant positive relationship with their job performance as shown in the computed correlation coefficients. Therefore, the hypothesis stating that there is no significant relationship between the teachers' mental health status and their level of job performance is rejected.

Proposed Intervention Program

The Proposed Intervention Program is designed to strengthen school heads' leadership practices to better support teachers' mental health and job performance. Rooted in the study's findings, the program emphasizes empathetic and supportive leadership through coaching, mental health awareness, and collaborative activities. By fostering a positive school climate and enhancing teacher well-being, the program aims to indirectly improve instructional quality and overall job satisfaction among elementary teachers in the Division of Lucena City.

Conclusion and Implications

Summary

The study examined the effect of leadership style of school heads to the mental health status and job performance of the elementary school teachers in the Division of Lucena City. Through surveys, the researcher explored the different leadership styles practiced by the school heads, the mental health status and level of job performance of the teachers and the effect of leadership styles to the teacher's mental health status and job performance. The study highlights the importance of intervention program that could improve the teacher's performance holistically.

Summary of Findings

The following findings were obtained based on the results of the study.

1. Leadership Style Practiced by the School Heads

The findings revealed that transactional leadership emerged as the dominant leadership style among school heads in the Division of Lucena City, with the highest overall mean score of 22.51 and practiced in seven out of twelve schools (58.33%). This indicates that most school heads focus on supervision, accountability, and performance-based management. Meanwhile, Democratic Leadership appeared in five schools (41.17%), reflecting a growing shift toward participative and motivational leadership approaches. Overall, the results suggest that while transactional leadership remains prevalent, elements of democratic leadership are gradually being integrated to promote collaboration, teacher engagement, and a more supportive school environment.

2. Mental Health Status of Elementary School Teachers

2.1 Stress Level

The elementary school teachers in the Division of Lucena City registered a moderate level of stress with a mean score of 3.34. This suggests that while teachers experience certain levels of pressure due to workload, administrative tasks, and

classroom responsibilities, they are still able to manage their stress effectively. The finding implies that stress among teachers exists but remains within a manageable range, possibly mitigated by coping strategies and support systems provided by their school environment.

2.2 Emotional Well-Being

Among the three indicators, emotional well-being obtained the highest mean score of 3.83, interpreted as high. This reflects that teachers generally feel emotionally stable, optimistic, and motivated in their professional and personal lives. Their positive disposition indicates resilience and satisfaction in their work, which may stem from collegial relationships, a sense of purpose, and supportive leadership in their schools.

2.3 Work–Life Balance

The teachers also exhibited a high level of work–life balance, with a mean score of 3.55. This result suggests that most teachers are capable of balancing their professional duties and personal responsibilities. It demonstrates that despite the demands of teaching, they can allocate time for rest, family, and self-care, contributing to their overall well-being and job satisfaction.

Overall, the teachers' combined mean of 3.57 indicates a high level of mental health status, signifying that they maintain positive well-being despite work demands. Their emotional resilience, motivation, and ability to balance work and personal life highlight strong coping mechanisms and adaptability, supported by positive work environments and effective school leadership.

3. Level of Job Performance of Elementary School Teachers

3.1 Instructional Competence

The teachers in the Division of Lucena City obtained a mean score of 4.48, interpreted as Very Satisfactory, under the instructional competence domain. This implies that teachers effectively plan lessons, employ appropriate teaching methods, and utilize varied instructional materials to meet learners' needs. Their performance reflects a solid grasp of pedagogical principles, though there remains room for enhancement through continuous training and exposure to innovative instructional practices that promote learner engagement and higher-order thinking skills.

3.2 Classroom Management

In terms of classroom management, teachers achieved an Outstanding rating with a mean of 4.56. This shows that they can create and sustain orderly, safe, and positive learning environments conducive to effective teaching. Their ability to manage classroom behavior, allocate time efficiently, and establish supportive routines demonstrates strong organizational and interpersonal skills that foster student engagement and respect.

3.3 Professionalism and Ethical Conduct

The domain of professionalism and ethical conduct received a mean score of 4.59, which is also interpreted as Outstanding. This indicates that teachers uphold the highest ethical standards, show respect for diversity, and perform their duties with integrity and accountability. Their commitment to ethical practice and professionalism contributes to a positive school culture and strengthens public trust in the teaching profession.

3.4 Collaboration and Communication

Teachers demonstrated exceptional performance in collaboration and communication, obtaining the highest mean score of 4.60, rated as Outstanding. This suggests that teachers actively engage in collegial discussions, share best practices, and maintain effective communication with students, parents, and colleagues. Their collaborative efforts promote teamwork and collective responsibility in achieving institutional goals and improving learner outcomes.

3.5 Commitment to Continuous Learning

The indicator commitment to continuous learning yielded a mean of 4.49, interpreted as Very Satisfactory. This implies that while teachers continuously update their knowledge and skills through seminars, workshops, and other professional development activities, there is potential for further enhancement. Encouraging teachers to pursue advanced studies and participate in innovation-oriented programs may further strengthen their instructional and leadership capacities.

3.6 Learner Outcomes and Support

Learner outcomes and support garnered a mean of 4.60, interpreted as Outstanding. This indicates that teachers are highly effective in ensuring student success through responsive instruction, individualized support, and formative assessment. Their strong commitment to student-centered learning underscores their role in achieving quality education outcomes.

4. Effect of Leadership Style of School Heads to the Mental Health and Job Performance of the Elementary School Teachers

The findings revealed that the school heads' leadership style had no significant effects with teachers' mental health ($r = 0.042$, $p = 0.412$). This indicates that the leadership approach alone did not directly influence the emotional well-being or psychological state of teachers in the Division of Lucena City. Although effective leadership can foster a positive school climate, the result suggests that teachers' mental health may be more strongly influenced by personal coping mechanisms, workload management, and external factors rather than leadership style.

Similarly, the study found no significant effects between school heads' leadership style and teachers' job performance ($r = 0.035$, $p = 0.498$). This means that the type of leadership practiced by school heads did not have a direct impact on how teachers performed their professional duties. However, a significant moderate positive correlation ($r = 0.336$, $p = 0.00001$) was observed between teachers' mental health and job performance, implying that teachers with better mental well-being tend to perform more effectively. Overall, while leadership remains a vital organizational factor, the findings emphasize that teachers' mental health plays a more crucial role in sustaining productivity and teaching effectiveness.

Conclusion

The result of the study implies that variations in leadership approaches, whether transactional, democratic, or other styles, do not directly influence teachers' psychological well-being or their work efficiency. Therefore, the hypotheses stating that there is no significant effect on the leadership style of school heads on the mental health status and there is no significant effect on the leadership style of school head on job performance of elementary school teachers are accepted.

Recommendations

Based on the study's findings regarding the effect of school heads' leadership styles to the mental health status and job performance of elementary school teachers in the Division of Lucena City, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. Based on the findings, transactional leadership was found to be the dominant style among school heads in the Division of Lucena City, thus, it is recommended that administrators adopt a more balanced leadership approach by integrating democratic and servant leadership practices. This will promote collaboration, teacher empowerment, and participative decision-making. Leadership enhancement programs, mentoring, and seminars on transformational and participatory leadership may be provided to help school heads create a more inclusive and motivating work environment.
2. The study revealed that elementary school teachers in the Division of Lucena City possess a generally high level of mental health, it is recommended that schools continue to promote and strengthen programs that support teachers' emotional well-being and work-life balance. Although teachers show resilience and motivation in managing work demands, there remains a need to enhance stress management initiatives to prevent burnout and sustain positive mental health. Schools may implement regular wellness activities, counseling sessions, and mental health awareness programs, while school heads are encouraged to maintain supportive and empathetic leadership practices that foster a positive and nurturing work environment conducive to teacher well-being and productivity.
3. Since teachers demonstrated an Outstanding level of job performance, it is recommended that the Division strengthen initiatives that support continuous growth and motivation among educators. Aside from recognizing high-performing teachers, the Division may provide regular mentoring, peer collaboration sessions, and research-based professional learning opportunities to help teachers enhance their instructional strategies and classroom practices. Emphasizing innovation, collaboration, and reflective teaching will not only sustain their current level of excellence but also ensure adaptability to the evolving demands of education.
4. Based on the results, there is no significant relationship between leadership style and teachers' mental health status or job performance. Thus, schools may focus on strengthening organizational support systems and addressing other factors influencing teacher well-being, such as workload balance, motivation, and peer collaboration. Given the significant link between mental health status and job performance, it is recommended that the division prioritize mental wellness programs, counseling support, and positive workplace culture initiatives to maintain productivity and overall teacher satisfaction.

5. It is recommended that the proposed intervention program developed from this study be adopted and implemented across elementary schools in the Division of Lucena City. The program may prioritize activities that promote teachers' mental health and well-being, including leadership mentoring, school-based wellness initiatives, peer support mechanisms, and stress-management programs. School heads are encouraged to integrate these initiatives into existing school plans to strengthen teacher support systems and foster a mentally healthy work environment. Regular monitoring and evaluation of the program are also recommended to ensure its effectiveness, sustainability, and alignment with the Department of Education's goals of holistic teacher development and continuous school improvement.

6. Considering the limitation of this study, future researchers are recommended to further investigate other factors that may influence teachers' mental health status and job performance beyond leadership style. Variables such as organizational climate, emotional intelligence, work motivation, and school culture could provide deeper insights into the complex dynamics affecting teacher well-being and productivity. Moreover, conducting similar studies in other divisions or educational settings such as secondary schools or private institutions, would help determine whether the findings in Lucena City are consistent across different contexts. Future studies may also employ a mixed-method approach, combining quantitative and qualitative data, to capture not only statistical relationships but also teachers' lived experiences, perceptions, and coping strategies. This broader and more comprehensive research design would contribute to the development of evidence-based policies and intervention programs that can better support teacher welfare, enhance leadership effectiveness, and improve overall educational outcomes.

Acknowledgements

The researcher extends her sincere gratitude to the Almighty God, the creator of heaven and earth for blessing her with wisdom, patience, and strength in crafting this thesis proposal.

To Marinduque State University Extension of Graduate Programs to Quezonian Educational College, Inc faculty and staff under the leadership of Dr. Diosdado P. Zulueta, your exemplary leadership and dedication to academic excellence have served as a source of inspiration and played a crucial role in the success of this achievement.

To Dr. Leodegario M. Jalos, Jr., Associate Dean for Graduate School, Extension of Graduate Programs, and as the researcher adviser, for his constant reminders and assistance in disseminating information about the study, as well as his continuous guidance and support throughout the research process. His valuable advice greatly contributed to the enhancement and completion of this study.

To Dr. Rizalie M. Lim, Dean of Graduate Studies, Quezonian Educational College Inc., for her encouraging words and unwavering support that motivated the researcher to pursue professional growth and excellence in conducting this study.

To Dr. Joy S. Montejo, Dr. Gilbert C. Alva and Dr. Diosdado P. Zulueta, as respected panel members, whose constructive feedback and professional guidance have significantly enhanced the quality and refinement of this research.

To Ms. Susan DL. Oribiana, Schools Divisions Superintendent, and District Supervisors, for their encouragement, guidance, and administrative support, which made it possible to carry out this research effectively and successfully.

To Ms. Maria Teresa C. Chavez, her statistician, for her valuable assistance in data analysis and for providing insightful inputs that were essential to the success of this study.

To Dr. Annalyn J. Decena, her editor and Dr. Gilbert C. Alva, her copy editor, for thoroughly reviewing the manuscript and ensuring clarity and accuracy in its presentation. Your efforts have significantly improved the overall quality of this thesis.

To Ms. Liezel M. Manoy, for support and assistance provided whenever needed.

To her family, Ronalyn, Ronald, Rannie and Reven Cris most especially her parents Mr. Renato P. Cañas and Mrs. Gloria A. Cañas for unwavering support and encouragement all the time, which motivates her to continue this study.

To Ms. Ronalyn A. Alzona, for your unconditional love, unwavering support, and endless encouragement that have been her greatest source of strength and inspiration throughout this journey. Your patience, understanding, and constant belief in her abilities gave courage to persevere during the most challenging moments of this thesis. This accomplishment would not have been possible without your heartfelt guidance, sacrifices, and the love you've selflessly given every step of the way.

To her friends, colleagues, fellow Elementary teachers and everyone, for their encouragement, prayers, and unwavering support in my abilities, she is forever grateful.

Funding

This research received no external funding from any public, commercial, or not-for-profit funding agency, and no organization provided financial support for the conduct of the study, authorship, or publication of this article.

Competing Interests Statement

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this article.

Data Availability Statement

Data sharing is not applicable to this article as no new data were created or analyzed in this study; all data used were obtained from previously published sources as cited in the reference list.

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Appendices

Appendix A. Survey Questionnaire

This appendix presents the complete survey questionnaire used in the study to gather data from the respondents. The instrument was designed to determine the relationship between the school heads' leadership styles, the mental health status of elementary school teachers, and their level of job performance in selected public elementary schools in the Division of Lucena City.

The questionnaire consists of structured items using a five-point Likert scale ranging from 1 – Strongly Disagree to 5 – Strongly Agree. The items are grouped into sections measuring leadership styles of school heads (such as transformational, transactional, democratic, autocratic, laissez-faire, charismatic, and servant leadership), teachers' mental health status (including stress level, emotional well-being, and work–life balance), and teachers' job performance indicators.

The survey instrument was administered to 12 school heads and 385 elementary school teachers from selected public elementary schools in the Division of Lucena City. The responses were used as the primary data for statistical analysis in determining the relationship among the variables included in the study.